

SCREENING WITH MOODMIND AI

Date :

Number of respondents :

Patient Name :

Age :

The steps are as follows

1. Researchers introduce how to use MOODMIND
2. Patient opens MOODMIND
3. Patient answers MOODMIND questions
4. MOODMIND gives a conclusion

MOODMIND screening results : Suspect/ at risk/ not depressed*

Enumerator name :

*Please choose one of the answers